

RESEARCH OF INFLUENCE OF THE GAS FILTER DESIGN PARAMETERS ON THE PROTECTIVE TERM OF RESPIRATORS

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Introduction

The use of gas filters in the workplace is an important element of the system of measures to protect the health of workers in potentially hazardous conditions [1]. Gas filters help remove harmful and toxic substances from the air inhaled by workers, such as gases, vapors, smoke and other substances. The use of gas filters can prevent poisoning, respiratory tract damage, allergic reactions and other negative consequences of the effects of harmful and hazardous substances on the human body. Thus, the use of gas filters helps to increase the overall level of safety and health of workers in the workplace.

However, the use of any gas filter has certain limitations, among which the protective action time can be distinguished [2]. The latter is mainly calculated by gas filter manufacturers taking into account the sorbent used and is used only to provide the type and class of the gas filter. Activated carbon with various impurities is mainly used as a sorbent. In the future, the user is guided exclusively by the manufacturer's data according to the marking on the filter and decides on the term of use of such a filter.

The type and class of the filter is determined by testing products under standard methods and stable conditions, namely constant air flow through the filter and the concentration of a harmful substance in the air of the test chamber. Such conditions are not found in workplaces. Thus, the intensity and depth of the worker's inhalation varies depending on the type of work performed, which leads to a constant change in the flow rate of the harmful substance passing through the gas filter. Similarly, the concentration of harmful substances in the inhaled air can vary depending on the distance to the source of pollution.

In scientific research and modeling of the process of filtering harmful substances through layers of coal for gas filters, air flow models through special columns filled with the above-mentioned coal are mainly used. Such models can theoretically take into account the influence of the point of entry of contaminated air and its exit from the test column. However, they do not take into account real filtration through gas filters, where the points of entry and exit of air are determined not only by scientific calculations, but also by practical issues regarding the manufacturability of manufacturing such a filter and the ergonomics of its use.

The quality and physical characteristics of activated carbon (grain size, their porosity, geometric shape of grains, absence of moisture in grains, etc.) have a direct impact on the breakthrough time of a gas filter.

Therefore, there is a need to determine the real breakthrough time of filters taking into account the parameters of activated carbon and the geometric shape of the gas filter housing.

Analysis of publication

Many authors consider the process of filtering polluted air through activated carbon, which is located in a gas filter, as the passage of a flow through a porous medium, while using calculation methods borrowed from hydrodynamics and considering the existing filter as an elementary component [3].

Others pay attention to the speed of movement of the polluted air flow and the conditions of its passage through the filter [4]. Researchers conclude that the difference in the obtained values of the protective action time is due to the action of the parameters of the air flow that contacts a certain area of activated carbon, due to its influence on the kinetics (the process itself) of adsorption. Within the limits of the reliability of the Wheeler-Jonas equation, this effect can be easily and accurately modeled, giving excellent estimates of the experimental breakthrough time.

Other researchers also use the Wheeler-Jonas equation as a basis and have proposed adapting it to take into account a number of parameters related to this environment: non-constant inlet concentration, breathable air flow, new physical forms of activated carbon, relative humidity and ambient temperature, chemisorbed gases and organic vapor mixtures. The authors believe that all these parameters can be calculated independently of each other based on data that are either readily available or measurable, their impact on the complexity of the model remains low [5], but they all play a significant role in modeling filtration.

Nevertheless, all researchers consider the breakthrough time as the time of complete saturation of activated carbon with a harmful substance when its concentration after the filter is equal to the concentration in the test chamber [6]. However, the filter breakthrough concentrations specified in regulatory documents are much lower. Thus, in the study [7], the authors determined the time for toluene to pass through the filter (10%, 50%, and 5 ppm) at toluene concentrations from 20 to 500 ppm, which is equal to or less than the maximum permissible concentrations in different countries.

The purpose of the paper

To investigate the influence of design factors of filter boxes of personal respiratory protective equipment that affect their real time of protective action.

Methodology

To determine the time of protective action t_b , the following formula was used:

$$t_b = \frac{W_e W}{C_0 Q} - \frac{W_e \rho_B}{k_v C_0} \ln \left(\frac{C_0 - C}{C} \right) \quad (1)$$

where W_e – sorption capacity of activated carbon, g/g, W – mass of activated carbon, g, C_0 – concentration of harmful substance, g/cm³, Q – air flow rate passing through activated carbon, cm³/min, ρ_B – packing density of activated carbon granules, g/cm³, k_v – adsorption rate coefficient, min⁻¹, C – penetration concentration determined for a certain substance, g/cm³.

The breakthrough time depends on the air flow rate - the higher it is, the sooner the need to replace the filter will arise. At the same time, the air flow rate is formed due to the speed of the air flow and the area of the filtering surface. At the same time, due to the existing structural differences of the filters (filter height, outlet size, gap size between the adsorbent and the lower surface of the filter formed by the guides, type of grille) significantly affect the distribution of the air flow rate over the filter volume.

For the study, two types of common gas filter designs with approximately the same adsorbent volume (about 100 cm³) were used - cylindrical and trapezoidal, which are used to protect against organic chemicals. The filters belonged to the first protection class. The porosity of the activated carbon in the box was 0.26. Figure 1 shows representatives of gas boxes of cylindrical and trapezoidal shapes.

Fig. 1. General view of trapezoidal (a) and cylindrical (b) type of filters

The geometric parameters of the gas filter boxes were measured using an electronic Syntek caliper with a measurement range of 0-150 mm and an accuracy of 0.1 mm. The measurement data were recorded and processed by mathematical calculations.

Computer modeling of the movement of air flows through the gas filter boxes was performed using the SolidWorks program. For this purpose, the gas filter designs (Fig. 1) were digitized. For the most common models of each form, 3D images were constructed according to the originals with all real dimensions preserved, respectively (Fig. 2). The main dimensions and parameters of the filter canister are given in Table 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. 3D models of trapezoidal (a) and cylindrical (b) gas filter canister

Having set the number of iterations, based on the given accuracy of the calculation, the movement of the corresponding amount of air with a flow rate ranging from 15 to 50 dm³/min was set in the SolidWorks software environment. The iterations were stopped if the value of the variation step became less than the given permissible error, which was no more than 5%.

Table 1 - Characteristics of cylindrical filter canister

Parameters of cylindrical filter canister	Value
Filter canister radius R_{kr} , mm	38-45
Square of the filtering surface S , cm ²	45-64
Radius of exhalation hole r_{kr} , mm	12-16
Height of filter canister H , mm	32-38
Gap between adsorber and back cover of filter canister h , mm	4-6
Displacement of the exhalation hole at the center of the canister, mm	0
Breathing resistance, Pa, at volume of 15 l/min.	84-100
The number of airflow guides	6-8

Table 2 - Characteristics of trapezoidal filter canister

Parameters of trapezoidal filter canister	Value
Width of filter canister B_k , mm	80-86
Length of filter canister L_k , mm	92-110
Square of the filtering surface S , cm^2	60-72
Radius of exhalation hole r_k , mm	12-16
Height of filter canister H , mm	24-30
Gap between adsorber and back cover of filter canister h , mm	4-6
Displacement of the exhalation hole at the center of the canister, mm	15-25
Breathing resistance, Pa, at volume of 15 l/min.	31-49
The number of airflow guides	10-12

To begin the calculation, the initial values of the velocities $V_{\theta i}^{(0)}$, $V_{z i}^{(0)}$, $V_{r i}^{(0)}$, $\rho_i^{(0)}$ were set in the nodes of the regular element grid, which was superimposed on the surface of the filter canister. The average velocities were calculated according to the filter cross-sectional area and the air flow rate in the filter canister. The described algorithm converges regardless of the choice of the initial approximation, however, to speed up the iteration process, it is desirable to choose an approximation, according to the nature of the proposed solution. The calculation was considered completed if the required calculation accuracy was achieved or a given number of iterations were performed.

The modeling process consists of the following stages:

- collection of primary data necessary for building a model; at this stage, the geometric parameters of the products are measured and analyzed, namely size, length, width, height, presence or absence of protrusions and depressions, etc., and data on the properties of the product are also collected, namely its mass, density or porosity, resistance to air flow at a certain flow rate, etc.

- construction of a geometric 3D model that takes into account the above parameters; the collected primary data is transferred to electronic form, as a result of which an empty 3D model is formed, which subsequently needs to be endowed with certain properties;

- provision of 3D model characteristics; according to the primary data or those that need to be simulated, they are entered into the model properties in electronic form (if necessary, the modeling operator can create the properties he needs himself, which correspond to those determined in laboratory conditions, these include: porosity of the medium, properties of activated carbon, characteristics of the bounding surfaces of the activated carbon layer - upper and lower meshes, pressure drop, air temperature, air humidity and atmospheric pressure;;

- at the next stage, 3D models with certain properties are exposed to the influence of the air flow; at the same time, a data package regarding the movement of the air flow through the model is simulated, and the obtained data is averaged (as a result of the modeling, the operator receives an answer regarding the given process);

- the last stage is verification of the reliability and accuracy of the primary data for modeling, as well as analysis of the obtained results.

During the calculation, air flow velocity distribution diagrams were obtained. The criterion for assessing the uniformity of dust particle deposition on the filter was the ratio V_{\max}/V_{\min} , which was minimized as a result of the calculations. The most uniform velocity distribution was in those areas where this ratio was minimal, in this case, there was no stagnation zones and uneven velocity in the studied area. In this case, the ratios V_{\max}/V_{\min} were compared, the results of the comparison are presented in the form of graphs.

The following design features were taken into account:

1. In cylindrical gas filters, the inlet and outlet holes are symmetrical relative to the axis and have the shape of a diffuser, where the inlet hole is bigger than the outlet hole that connects to the respirator.

While in flat-shaped gas filters, the outlet hole is displaced relative to the common axis of the filter. This is due to the manufacturer's desire to increase the user's field of vision by redistributing the total mass of the filter.

2. The height of the trapezoidal gas filters mainly does not exceed 30 mm, which is again due to the manufacturer's desire to increase the user's field of vision, while cylindrical gas filters have a height of at least 30 mm.

To verify and refine the calculation models in the SolidWorks software environment, we provided for the determination of the breathing resistance of gas filter canister according to DSTU EN 13274-3:2005 "Personal protective equipment. Test methods. Part 3. Determination of breathing resistance". The general scheme of the testing equipment is shown in Fig. 3. The air flow rate through the filter was 15 l/min. and 47.5 l/min.

Fig. 3. General scheme of the testing equipment for determining breathing resistance: 1 – electronic micromanometer Testo 512, 2 – filter sample, 3 – suitable nozzle for connecting the filter, 4 – flow meter PM-6,3, 5 – air flow line to the aspirator АПВ-М-3-220в-250

The gas filter is installed on an suitable nozzle, which ensures a strong and airtight connection. The air flow rate through the filter was set by a flow meter PM-6,3 and regulated by an aspirator АПВ-М-3-220в-250. To determine the pressure drop across the tested filter an electronic micromanometer Testo 512 was used with a measurement range from minus 2000 Pa to 2000 Pa, the accuracy of the device is 1 Pa. The breathing resistance ΔR was calculated by the formula:

$$\Delta P = P_f - P_{st},$$

де P_f – pressure drop value of the test system with filter, Pa; P_{st} - pressure drop value of the test system without filter, Pa.

Microsoft Excel 365 was used to process experimental data and construct approximation curves of the dependence of the change in respiratory resistance on the filtration rate.

Results

According to the results of determining the breathing resistance, it was found that the type of filter leads to a nonlinear relationship between the pressure drop and air flow rate for the same filtering surface area, adsorber layer height, and its packing density (Table 3).

Table 3 - Characteristics of gas filter canisters

Type of the filter	Square of the filtering surface S, cm ²	Measured adsorber volume of the gas filter, cm ³	Average value of breathing resistance, Pa, at the flow rates	
			15 l/min.	47,5 l/min.
Trapezoidal form	64,2	96	37	124
Cylindrical form	45,3	86	90	320

Analysis of the obtained data shows that the difference in the breathing resistance of different types of filter canisters is caused by their design features, which significantly increase the path of the adsorbed air flow through the displaced outlet hole of the filter canister (Fig. 2). It can

be assumed that such a design was proposed by the developers in order to increase the breakthrough time of filter with trapezoidal form of canister. In addition, in any case, the trapezoidal shape of the filter canister, other things being equal, provides a relatively lower filtration speed (Table 4), which also has a positive effect on the value of the term of use such filters.

Table 4 - Volumetric air velocity through the filter canister

Parameters	The average speed of the air flow through the filters, m/s	
	Трапецевидної форми	Циліндричної форми
Square of the filtering surface, cm ²		
110 cm ²	0,21	0,28
80 cm ²	0,42	0,44
50 cm ²	0,62	0,65
Outlet hole diameter, mm		
24 mm	12,3	17,1
28 mm	10,3	14,2
32 mm	8,1	11,2
Displaces of the outlet hole at the canister center		
5 mm	16,2	17,8
10 mm	14,1	18,6
15 mm	12,3	21,2
Gap between adsorber and back cover of filter canister		
4 mm	36,1	32,1
5 mm	21,2	24,2
6 mm	12,3	17,1
Height of filter canister		
24 mm	12,3	17,1
28 mm	10,3	15,1
32 mm	8,3	12,1

Thus, during the modeling of the influence of the filtering surface square on the value of the filtering speed (Fig. 4) in each of the specified types of filter canisters, it can be seen that the filtering speed is on average 15% lower in the case of a non-cylindrical canisters.

a

b

Fig. 4. Models of filtration rate distribution in different types of filter canisters: trapezoidal (a), cylindrical (b) with the same surface area, height, outlet hole and sorbent density

Similar results were obtained in the case of different diameters of the outlet hole. The latter affected not only the uniformity of the distribution of the filtration rate over the volume of the adsorbent, but also the magnitude of the pressure drop (Fig. 5). Of course, its increase led to an improvement in these indicators due to a decrease in the filtration rate caused by a change in the outlet hole. However, the size of the outlet hole is determined by the design of the mask, based on the minimum limitation of the field of view.

Fig. 5. Curve of the distribution of relative air flow velocity depending on the size of the outlet diameter

The displacement of the outlet hole according to the center of the canister leads to the redistribution of the air flow into the filter media (Fig. 6) and the formation of vortex flows (Fig. 7), which reduce the duration of the protective effect by up to 30%.

Figure 6. Curve of the dependence of the distribution of the relative air flow velocity on the displacement of the outlet with a diameter of 30 mm from the center of the filter box at an air flow rate of 30 l/min

Fig. 7. View of the distribution of the filtration rate by volume of a trapezoidal form of a gas filter at an air flow rate of 47.5 l/min.

The presence of a gap between the adsorber and the lower part of the filter at a low air flow rate passing through the filter will ensure a uniform distribution of air mass movement between the elementary layers of activated carbon in a trapezoidal form filter canister. While in a cylindrical form gas filter at a flow rate of 15 l/min you can see areas in which the air flow rate is lower, and therefore it can be assumed that they are not fully involved in the process of filtering harmful substances (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. View of the distribution of filtration speed by volume of the trapezoidal model (a) and cylindrical model (b) of the gas filter at a flow rate of 15 l/min.

The height of the filter canister leads to a decrease in the speed of air masses passing through the filter. In a cylindrical form gas filter, the load of the air volume is distributed symmetrically relative to the central axis across the entire width of the canister with a decrease in speed closer to the walls (Fig. 9). In a flat form gas filter, the speed of air passage along the length of the canister appears uneven. Thus, the speed is significantly reduced at a length of 40 mm out of the total 100 mm of the canister length. Thus, it can be assumed that the adsorber in this volume will not be completely consumed when a harmful substance penetrates through the filter.

Fig. 9. Simulation data of the air velocity through a cylindrical filter at a flow rate of 47.5 l/min.

According to the modeling results, it is possible to predict the time of protective action of gas filters by applying formula (1). Let us specify the main characteristics of activated carbon and filter boxes that will affect the final result: gas filters for protection against organic vapors, test substance cyclohexane, concentration of harmful substance in the air 250 mg/m³, maximum permissible concentration 1.4 mg/m³, packing density of activated carbon granules – 0.74 g/cm³, kv – adsorption rate coefficient 3400 min⁻¹ are given in Tables 5 and 6.

The air flow rate Q is calculated as a variable value determined by the formula:

$$Q = S \cdot V,$$

where S is the square of the filtering surface of canister, cm², V is the speed of air movement through the box, cm/s. The initial data on the speed are in Table 4.

Table 5 - The value of the determined breakthrough time of gas filters at square of the filtering surface

Square of the filtering surface	Theoretical volume of breakthrough time, min.	
	Trapezoidal form	Cylindrical model
110 cm ²	272	200
80 cm ²	182	173
50 cm ²	199	189

The initial data for the calculation are the characteristics of cylindrical type filter canisters from Table 1 and the characteristics of trapezoidal type filter canisters from Table 2. The initial data for the speed are according to Table 4.

We can predict the following:

- the breakthrough time value will increase with an increasing of the outlet hole diameter, since the speed of passage through the activated carbon layers will decrease due to the uniformity of the outlet flow and the involvement of a larger volume of activated carbon for filtration.

- displacement of the outlet hole from the center of the canister will lead to an increase in the volume of activated carbon that is not involved in filtering or filtering in it is not performed in full. Additionally, the displacement of the outlet hole can lead to uneven filtering and the appearance of turbulent flows, which generally reduces the breakthrough time of the gas filter.

- increasing the gap between the adsorber and the lower wall of the filter will increase the breakthrough time of the gas filter. This will occur due to improving the uniformity of air filtration through the activated carbon layers and increasing the total volume of activated carbon involved in the filtration process.

- increasing the height of the filter canister, and therefore the activated carbon layer, will lead to an increase the breakthrough time of the gas filter. However, the disadvantage of increasing the height of the filter canister is an increase in breathing resistance.

As a result of the calculations, it is clear that an increase the Square of the filtering surface, as well as the outlet, of course, under other equal conditions, will lead to an increase of breakthrough time by up to 30% in the specified range from 50 cm² to 110 cm². While a slight shift in the diameter of the outlet hole in accordance with the center of the filter box has almost no effect on the specified value, since it is within the error range of up to 5%.

Table 6 - The value of the breakthrough time gas filters calculated according to different design parameters

Parameters	Theoretical volume of breakthrough time, min.	
	Trapezoidal form	Cylindrical model
Outlet hole diameter		
24 mm	162	168
28 mm	189	196
32 mm	216	224
Displacement of the outlet hole from the center of the canister		
5 mm	199	185
10 mm	193	181
15 mm	189	178
The gap between the adsorber and the lower wall of the filter canister		
4 mm	145	151
5 mm	182	189
6 mm	218	226
Height of the filter canister		
24 mm	182	141
28 mm	212	165
32 mm	242	189

The presence of a gap between the adsorber and the lower wall of the filter canister also allows for an increase in the duration of the protective effect, but unlike other design parameters, when a certain value is reached, it does not change in the future, which is explained by the absence of a change in the filtration speed due to the equalization of the resistance to the air flow in the undermask space.

Discussions

There are open access publications that consider the influence of the properties of activated carbon (granule diameter, packing density) [8], filter thickness [9], climatic parameters [10] and operating conditions [11] on the duration of the protective effect. It has been established that in most cases the relationship between the duration of the protective effect and air flow rate, under certain conditions, is linear. However, some studies indicate that deviations from generally accepted dependencies are possible. For example, with a pulsating flow [12] or the influence of the filter box parameters [13], when an uneven distribution of the air flow is observed over the filter volume. The study itself shows that the design parameters are able to make significant adjustments to the filtration process. The conclusion can be explained by the uneven distribution of the air flow velocity over the filter area both due to the displacement of the outlet relative to the center of the filter box and due to the presence of a small gap between the filter and the back wall of the box [14, 15]. Theoretical calculations assume a uniform filtration process over the entire filter area, however, studies show that the indicators can fluctuate by 20-30%. This is due to the rapid saturation of the granules with adsorbed gas in the area where the filtration rate is highest, which leads to the breakthrough phase. At the same time, the rest of the filter has not yet fully worked out.

This condition of the filter during saturation is explained by the fact that in order to reach the outlet of the corresponding box, which is offset from the center, the peripheral air streams need to overcome a greater distance than the central streams. In addition, when colliding with the back wall of the box, they will also need to turn, which also reduces the speed of movement. And the further the stream is from the outlet, the more resistance it needs to overcome. In addition, a dynamic tube is usually used to determine the time of protective action in laboratory conditions, in which the coal is not as compacted as it would be in a gas-proof box, so the pore size will not

correspond to the conditions of real application (9). The adsorption front in this case is difficult to estimate, since the diameter of the dynamic tube is 20 mm, and the diameter of a real filter, for example, of a cylindrical shape of class 1, is at least 75 mm. The adsorption front affects the total time of protective action. The gentler it is, the more evenly the layers of activated carbon will be used up and the later "breakthrough" time will occur. All this leads to an increase in the service life of the gas filter and a decrease in the risk of harmful substances leaking due to uneven filtration.

The adsorption front is always considered as a uniform working out of the elementary layers of activated carbon, however, the linear area of the filtering surface through which a constant air flow will pass can change the filtration speed along the width of the canister. Therefore, the question of the movement of the coal adsorption front along the linear plane remains open.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the variety of gas filter canisters, where each manufacturer produces filters of its own design with unique parameters, which, according to the manufacturer, provide the necessary degree of protection.

Results

The influence of the gas filter canister design parameters on their breakthrough time was investigated. The relationship between the increase in the area of the filter surface, as well as the outlet opening of the filter canister, which increase the breakthrough time by up to 30% in a certain range of filter canister sizes, was revealed. It was established that increasing the gap between the adsorbent and the lower wall of the filter canister and displacement the outlet opening relative to the center of the filter canister allows to increase the breakthrough time within the limits of the calculation error of up to 5%, while the indicators stabilize after reaching a certain indicator characterizing the considered design parameter. The rational parameters of the gas filter canister to ensure the maximum possible breakthrough time were determined, which include the area of the filtering surface of 120 mm², the filter height of 30 mm, the gap between the adsorber and the lower wall of the filter canister - not less than 4 mm.